

Strength Parameters of Kaolinite Clay Stabilized with Nano-Silica and Reinforced with Hemp Fibers under Freeze-Thaw Cycles: An Experimental Study

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ABSTRACT

Freeze-thaw cycles (F-T cycles) can significantly affect the geotechnical properties of soils. Therefore, in areas with high freeze-thaw potential, it is essential to consider the effects of these cycles during the durability and deformation analysis of slopes and excavations. One of the effective methods to improve the mechanical properties of clay soils subjected to F-T cycles is stabilization with nanoparticles and natural fibers. This study investigated the effects of F-T cycles on the strength properties of clay soils reinforced with nano-silica and hemp fibers. Experiments were conducted to determine the effect of nano-silica (SiO₂) and hemp fibers on the unconfined compressive strength (UCS) under F-T cycles. The soil specimens were treated with 0.5%, 1%, and 1.5% nano-silica. Then, the samples were prepared with fiber-to-soil ratios of 0.2, 0.4, and 0.6 and the optimal dosage of nano-silica of 1%. Next, they were subjected to 1, 3, 5, and 7, 10 F-T cycles for durability testing. Finally, UCS tests were conducted to determine the strength of both reinforced and unreinforced samples. Based on the results of UCS tests, the optimum nano-silica content was 1%, which increased the soil strength by 92%. According to the UCS tests, when 1% nano silica was used in soil, the maximum compressive strength was obtained, which is the criteria for optimum mechanical performance. The results of the UCS tests on the durability test samples under F-T cycles showed a decrease of 27 to 50% in UCS with the increasing number of cycles for the unreinforced samples. However, the combination of 1% nano-silica and 0.4% hemp fibers resulted in a 13% reduction in the UCS of the soil after 10 freeze-thaw cycles, while strength was reduced by 50% for the untreated soil. The interlocking zones and increased friction between the particles were improved by the usage of hemp fiber between the soil grains and nano silica. As a result, these phenomena effectively prevent excessive cracking during the application of F-T cycles, thereby enhancing the mechanical performance and durability of the samples.

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Graphical Abstract

Conclusion

- The stabilizers used are environmentally friendly materials and significantly improved the compressive strength.
- The addition of hemp fibers improved the soil's ductility.
- The soil reinforced with fiber and nano-silica showed greater durability against F-T cycles.

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NOMENCLATURE

<i>OMC</i>	Optimum Moisture Content	Re	Resistance Reduction Coefficient
<i>MDD</i>	Maximum Dry Density	LCA	Life cycle assessment
<i>UCS</i>	Unconfined Compressive Strength	$\sigma_{\text{Untreated}}$	Maximum UCS stress for natural soil
<i>F – T</i>	Freezing-Thawing Cycles	$\sigma_{\text{F-T}}$	Maximum unconfined stress after F-T
<i>E50</i>	Elastic Modulus at 50% of Maximum Stress		

1. INTRODUCTION

In cold regions, soils are continuously subjected to F-T cycles, which significantly affect the design of foundation systems in these areas. Clayey soils in such regions often have no desirable geotechnical and mechanical properties required for civil engineering projects. F-T cycles greatly affect soil durability and stability (1). Freezing creates a mixture of soil, water, and ice, with mechanical behavior influenced by freezing, temperature, and stress. Stabilization is key to improve soil performance in engineering (2, 3). Cement, lime, and fly ash are some of the most commonly used and studied materials for ground improvement under various conditions in many research works (4-6).

However, the use of calcium-based stabilizers to improve soil properties may present challenges due to their negative on the environment and humans. The production and application processes of these materials not only raise significant concerns regarding environmental degradation but also exacerbate environmental issues related to climate change and pollution (7). Furthermore, the production processes of calcium-based stabilizers can significantly accelerate global warming. These materials release carbon dioxide (CO₂) into the atmosphere, generating greenhouse gases and contributing to the intensification of climate change (8, 9). Calcium-based stabilizers, including hydrated lime and Portland cement, are frequently employed in soil stabilization; however, their production methods are linked to considerable CO₂ emissions (10). The manufacturing of hydrated lime generates around 0.74 kg of CO₂ per kilogram, whereas Portland cement produces about 0.83 kg of CO₂ per kilogram. Nano-silica has emerged as a viable soil stabilizer with potentially reduced carbon emissions (11). The carbon footprint of nano-silica indicates remarkably lower values, about 0.00084 kg CO₂ per kilogram for obtaining nano-silica (10, 12). Therefore, the use of low-cost materials with less environmental effect is strongly recommended. Furthermore, with the rapid advancement of nanotechnology in geotechnical engineering and the challenges associated with traditional stabilizers, nanoparticles have emerged as an operative solution for ground improvement (10). One of the new methods of soil stabilization is the application of the microbial-induced calcium carbonate precipitation (MICP) technique. This technique was tested through a series of laboratory experiments, which revealed that MICP can

significantly improve compressive strength and reduce the soil's free swell by up to 50% (13). The results of applying nitrogen-phosphorus fertilizer tablets demonstrated that using different percentages of this material can improve soil performance (14). Nanoparticles' high specific surface area (SSA) allows them to fill soil voids thus improving the geotechnical properties (11). Additionally, nano-silica is significantly more cost-effective than calcium-based stabilizers, making it an economical option for soil modification (12). It has been demonstrated that nano-alumina increased OMC but lowered MDD, while nano-silica reduced plasticity and improved soil strength (13).

On the other hand, the use of synthetic fibers, such as polymer products, for reinforcing clayey soil was recognized as an effective method to strengthen and stabilize the soil. However, these materials may pose environmental issues due to their non-renewability and incompatibility with the environment (14). The findings of a laboratory study indicated that addition of polypropylene fibers led to an increase in UCS by up to 356% and Young's modulus (E_{50}) by up to 109% (15). In recent years, the use of natural fibers for soil reinforcement has attracted a huge deal of attention because of their unique properties including abundance, low cost, lightweight, flexibility, and high durability (when improved with chemical treatment) (11, 13). Natural fibers have recently gained attention for soil reinforcement. In a recent study, addition of jute fibers combined with stabilizers such as slag lime to clay soil significantly increased UCS and soil stiffness. This improvement in soil properties was observed until the fiber content was limited to 1%, whereas adding higher amounts of fibers reduced these parameters. Additionally, with an increase in fiber content of up to 1.5%, the plasticity of the soil consistently improved. The combination of these fibers with slag lime not only improved strength but also significantly enhanced soil stiffness. Therefore, the optimal percentage of jute fibers is around 1%, which provides the highest level of strength in stabilized soil (16). Recent studies showed that rice husk ash (RHA) and natural fibers significantly affect soil properties. The addition of hemp fibers to the soil increased the permeability coefficient as well as improved UCS, shear strength, and CBR properties. Among the various amounts of hemp fibers, a content of 0.75% was identified as the optimal percentage for achieving the best results in improving the strength and stabilization of the soil (17). Studies discovered that

additives like fibers and cement improved the strength of clayey soil. Adding 0.5% fiber to the soil resulted in the greatest increase in tensile and compressive strength. Furthermore, the experimental results indicated that the combination of fibers with cement had a maximum effect on improving the compressive strength of the soil compared to the use of these additives individually. It is indicated that combining these two materials can effectively enhance soil performance (4).

F-T cycles have significant effects on the mechanical and physical features of fine-grained soils, including volume, strength, compressibility, density, moisture, and bearing capacity. In this regard, studies have been directed to evaluate changes in UCS and shear strength of the soil as well as the effect of nano-silica (SiO_2) on improving these properties under F-T conditions. It was revealed that adding nano-silica to clay soil effectively prevented the loss of strength due to F-T cycles, while simultaneously enhancing its mechanical properties. In particular, after 9 F-T cycles, an increment was observed in UCS and shear strength in clay samples containing 1% nano-silica, along with improvements of 16% and 21%, respectively, compared to the untreated clay (6). Additionally, research has indicated no significant changes in the soil's void ratio after multiple F-T cycles in some cases (18). Furthermore, findings have shown that, after melting ice crystals, large pores remained in the soil structure increasing the permeability (19). The modulus of elasticity is a critical parameter in the design of embankments, significantly influencing their mechanical performance. Typically, this property decreases with the occurrence of F-T cycles, even with a small number of cycles. The reduction in the modulus of elasticity caused by these cycles can result in substantial alterations in the behavior of embankments, adversely affecting their durability and load-bearing capacity (20). F-T cycles significantly reduce the shear strength of unsaturated fine-grained soils. This process weakens the cohesion between soil particles and reduces the soil's bearing capacity under applied loads, which can especially create problems for engineering projects in areas with extreme temperature variations (21). The effect of hemp fibers on the features of clayey soils subjected to F-T cycles was studied indicating that an increase in the length and percentage of hemp fibers considerably incremented the liquid limit of the soil. Furthermore, hemp fibers greatly improved the UCS of the samples. These results suggest that hemp fibers can substantially improve the load-bearing capacity of clayey soils because of their superior tensile strength in comparison to other commonly used natural fibers (e.g., jute, sisal). Furthermore, after undergoing four F-T cycles, the hemp fiber-reinforced samples exhibited a lower rate of reduction in UCS compared to untreated soil samples. It is demonstrated that hemp fibers can significantly enhance the durability and mechanical

performance of clayey soils under F-T conditions, thereby improving their durability and resistance to degradation in extreme environmental conditions (22).

Although previous studies have examined the individual effects of nano silica and hemp fiber on soil stabilization, this work is the first to examine their combined influence and synergistic mechanism and impact on soil strength and durability. The objective of the amalgamation of these bio-compatible materials is to enhance the mechanical performance and freeze-thaw durability, as well as to provide distinctive insights into sustainable geotechnical engineering and geo-based infrastructures. Additionally, the cohesive forces and bonding between particles are intended to be optimized. The cohesion and bonding between particles can be enhanced by incorporating nano silica into soil. On the other hand, the utilization of fibers can increase the frictional and interlocking forces. As a result, further research is necessary to investigate the synergistic application of these components, which serve as biocompatible cohesive agents and bio-tensile elements, to enhance cohesive and interlocking forces while taking mechanical strength into account. Various studies have been conducted on the effect of nano-silica on improving various properties of clay soils and the role of hemp fibers in soil reinforcement. However, no study has been performed on the combined effect of these two materials, especially in increasing the durability of clay soils under F-T cycles. In this study, the simultaneous application of a soil stabilizer (nano-silica) and a reinforcing agent (hemp fibers) to clay soils was evaluated through some UCS tests to evaluate the effect of these materials on the strength and durability of clay soils under repeated F-T cycles. Furthermore, the optimal conditions for using this combination were determined and analyzed using microstructural investigations.

2. MATERIALS AND METHODS

2.1. Clay In this work, kaolinite clay was selected for laboratory investigations as fine-grained soils are more susceptible to F-T cycles (23). Many constructions and geotechnical applications involve kaolinite-rich soils, so conducting tests may have practical implications according to industrial and engineering relevance. Kaolinite clay is often used in soil stabilization studies due to its well-defined mineralogy, relatively lower mechanical performance compared to other clays, and its widespread availability. Kaolinite has a cation exchange capacity and a stable structure, making it susceptible to expansion and contraction. In addition, kaolinite generally exhibits lower compressive strength. Kaolinite is vulnerable to damage, as repeated F-T cycles can cause severe volume changes, leading to loss of strength and increased permeability.

The clay used in this research is classified as CL according to the USCS standard. This clay was sourced from the Kaboodkamar mine in Iran, which is actively extracted from two mines with a reserve of over half a million tons. The color of the clay lumps ranges from cream to yellow, while its powdered form appears white with a cream tint. The results of the particle size distribution obtained from the hydrometer test are displayed in Figure 1. Table 1 presents the physical properties of this clay. To analyze the soil elements, X-ray fluorescence (XRF) testing was performed on the samples, for which the results are provided in Table 2.

2.2. Nano Silica Nano-silica is an innovative material with particles at the nanometer scale. It is widely used in civil engineering projects as a soil stabilizer and a performance enhancer for materials because of its unique properties. The average particle size of nano-silica in this study ranges from 20 to 30 nanometers, as determined by SEM (Scanning Electron Microscopy) and its specific surface area from Brunauer-Emmett-Teller (BET) testing. With the silicate structure of this material and its very high surface area, it can enhance the bond between soil particles by absorbing water and forming viscous sticky gels. In this study, nano-silica was obtained from Nanossani Company in Iran, and its chemical and physical properties were examined according to

Figure 1. Particle size distribution of the soil

TABLE 1. Geotechnical properties of the soil

Properties	Standard	Value
Liquid limit (%)	ASTM D 4318-85	39
Plastic limit (%)	ASTM D 4318-85	30
Plasticity index (%)	ASTM D 4318-85	12
G_s	ASTM D 854-14	2.6
Soil class	ASTM D 2487-11	CL
OMC (%)	ASTM D 698-78	22
MDD (kN/m^3)	ASTM D 698-78	15.3

TABLE 2. XRF test results of the soil

Symbol	Value (%)
SiO ₂	70.83
Al ₂ O ₃	19.14
Fe ₂ O ₃	0.57
CaO	0.38
MgO	0.13
Na ₂ O	0.63
K ₂ O	0.93
TiO ₂	0.33
SO ₃	0.91
P ₂ O ₅	0.26
LOI	3.4

laboratory standards (Tables 3 and 4). The chemical composition of the nano-silica was determined through XRF testing representing a high percentage of silica and an acceptable purity for soil stabilization applications. In general, the bonding mechanism between nano silica and clay involves several phases. At the microscopic level, nano-silica interacts with clay particles by physical and chemical mechanisms, which are hydrogen bonding and Van der Waals forces. Nano-silica possesses many hydroxyl (-OH) groups on its surface that engage in hydrogen bonding with the surface hydroxyls of clay

TABLE 3. Physical properties of the nano silica

Properties	Result
Nano type	Silicon Dioxide (SiO ₂)
Purity (%)	99.5
Average particle size (nm)	20-30
Specific surface area (m^2/gr)	180-600
Bulk density (kN/m^3)	1
Specific gravity (kN/m^3)	24
Color	White
Nano type	Silicon Dioxide (SiO ₂)

TABLE 4. Chemical properties of the nano silica

Properties	Result(%)
SiO ₂	99.5
Ti	0.022
Ca	0.014
Na	0.006
Fe	0.004

minerals, including kaolinite. The weak links facilitate early adhesion between nano-silica and clay particles by producing a viscous gel (11). The polymerization of silica and semi-pozzolanic reactions are additional factors contributing to soil enhancement. Upon the addition of optimal moisture content to the soil, nano-silica particles experience polymerization, resulting in the formation of Si–O–Si networks. Additionally, the stability of nano-silica leads to the freezing and expansion of water within clay pores, resulting in particle displacement and a deterioration of soil structure. Nano-silica diminishes free water in pores by adhering to clay, hence restricting ice crystal formation. In successive F-T cycles, nano-silica particles occupy microvoids, decreasing permeability and impeding fracture growth. The enhanced interparticle bonding preserves soil integrity despite temperature variations

2. 3. Hemp Fiber Figure 2 illustrates the use of hemp fibers as a reinforcement agent in this study. These fibers have a specific gravity of 1.6 and a water absorption capacity of 10%. Based on the optimal length provided in other studies, a fiber length of 10 mm was selected (16, 17). Tables 5 and 6 display the physical and chemical properties of the hemp fibers used, respectively. To determine the optimal percentage of nano-silica, samples with 0.5, 1, and 1.5 weight percent of dry soil were prepared. After finding the optimal percentage of nano-silica (1%), the soil was reinforced with different amounts of hemp fibers, including 0.2, 0.4, and 0.6 dry weight of the soil. These values were selected based on related studies to determine the optimal percentages of fibers and nanomaterials (18, 19).

3. TEST METHOD

This study aimed to assess the effect of adding nano-silica and hemp fibers on the strength properties of clay soil subjected to 1, 3, 5, 7, and 10 F-T cycles. Initially, natural clay soil along with nano-silica stabilized soil at 0.5%, 1%, and 1.5% were tested to determine the optimal percentage of nano-silica in the soil. This evaluation was carried out through UCS testing. Then, for three different percentages of hemp fibers (0.2%, 0.4%, and 0.6%), the samples were prepared using the optimum moisture content (OMC) and maximum dry density (MDD) determined from the compaction test and subjected to 0, 1, 3, 5, 7, and 10 F-T cycles.

3. 1. Sample Preparation Tests were conducted on cylindrical samples (76 mm height, 38 mm diameter) using the OMC and MDD from the compaction test. The soil was oven-dried and considered fully dry for all tests, following ASTM D-2216 standards. To prepare the samples, the mixtures were divided into four parts, each

Figure 2. Image of the materials; a)soil, b)nanoparticles, and c)fibers

TABLE 5. Chemical properties of hemp fibers

Properties	Result (%)
Cellulose	70-74
Hemi-cellulose	18-22
Lignin	4-6
Wax	0.8

TABLE 6. Physical properties of hemp fibers

Properties	Result (%)
Tensile Strength (MPa)	690
Young's Modulus (GPa)	70
Elongation at break (%)	1.6

separately cast and compacted in the mold. This method was used to achieve a fully compacted and uniform sample (24). For preparing the nano-silica stabilized samples, the soil was divided into five parts, and a specified amount of nano-silica was sprayed onto each part. Then, each part was mixed separately for a minimum of 1 hour using a mixer. This method was recognized as the best approach to achieve homogeneous and uniform samples (25).

Each sample was covered with plastic immediately after molding to prevent water loss. For the F-T cycles, the samples were first placed in a freezer at -20°C for 12 h. The specimens were then placed in a chamber at 20°C for 12 h for the thawing process. These temperatures were selected in accordance with similar studies (26, 27). A 12-hour duration was selected for each stage, especially in the freezing and thawing processes based on previous studies to ensure the full completion of freezing and thawing cycles. This timing was specifically chosen to ensure the complete transition of water into ice and then its full thawing. Therefore, all the physiological and chemical conditions necessary for analysis in the F-T cycles were met (28-33).

In this study, two methodologies were utilized to ascertain the range of nano-silica, and hemp fiber selection. The nano-silica, and hemp fiber ratios were initially established using data from prior studies. Prior studies suggested that the range ratio for nano-silica was

0.25–2% (34, 35). Moreover, prior research indicated that the ideal nano-silica ratio for cohesive soils ranged from 1-1.25%. The UCS trial assessments were performed to determine the nano-silica ratio, revealing that the viable and practical range lies between 0.5% and 1.5%. The UCS diminished following the incorporation of more than 1.5% of nano-silica into the utilized sediments. Furthermore, the range ratio for hemp fiber, according to the previous articles, was 0.2–0.8% (36, 37). On the other hand, the UCS experimental trials were to determine the hemp fiber ratio, revealing that the usable and workable percentages were below 0.8%. The incorporation of an increased hemp fiber dosage leads to fiber clustering and inadequate distribution, as demonstrated by ocular observation and prior experiences. In other words, excessive fiber content leads to cluster formation and unequal distribution, rather than reinforcing the soil matrix and enhancing homogeneity. This results in the formation of weak areas instead of increasing overall strength. Consequently, in this study, the maximum threshold and dosage were initially determined by experimental trials tests. Subsequently, various studies were conducted to examine the interaction of nano-silica, hemp fiber and soil at specific percentages.

3. 2. Unconfined Compressive Testing

The strength of the samples was measured using an UCS device, following the procedure outlined in ASTM D5311-92. During the testing process, the strain was maintained at a constant rate of 0.5 mm per minute to ensure the accuracy of the results and the uniformity of the test. This method was used to accurately evaluate the strength properties of the samples in the lab (25). The soil mixture compacted to maximum dry density and optimum moisture content was compacted into a stainless-steel tube in three layers. Then, using the hydraulic jack movement inside the metal tube, the soil mixture was uniformly compacted to obtain a sample with a diameter of 38 mm and a height of 76 mm. This compaction method was used to achieve proper density and uniformity of the samples during the testing process. Afterward, the samples were removed from the stainless-steel mold without any disturbance while using hydraulic jack pressure for testing. Three samples were prepared per mixture, and the average test data were calculated, with a strain rate of 0.5 mm per minute based on previous studies (27). The sample labeling was done using the characters "S", "N" and "F" to represent the kaolinite soil, percentage of nano-silica, and hemp fibers, respectively. To guarantee uniformity in sample preparation and data repeatability for each mixture, three specimens were made, and the mean data was utilized, and average results are reported. Meticulous preparation and testing of the samples reduced variability among repeated measurements, yielding coefficient of variation (CoV) values under 5% in the test outcomes.

4.RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

4. 1. Effects of Hemp Fiber on Compaction

Figure 3 represents the effect of nano-silica on the maximum dry density (MDD) and optimum moisture content (OMC) of the samples. Nano-silica increased the OMC and decreased the MDD. As seen, the OMC for the pure soil and various nano-silica mixtures were 22%, 23%, 25%, and 26% for 0.5%, 1%, and 1.5% nano-silica, respectively. Additionally, by adding nano-silica at 0.5%, 1%, and 1.5%, the OMC of the soil increased by 4%, 8%, and 4%, respectively. The use of nano-silica also reduced the MDD of the soil by 0.6%, 3.9%, and 2%, respectively. Therefore, an increase in nano-silica content resulted in a continuous decrease in the MDD of the nano-silica stabilized soil. The reason is that nano-silica displaces air within the soil pores, leading to improved soil compaction. Due to its high specific surface area (SSA), nano-silica absorbed moisture from the soil and surrounding environment thus increasing the OMC of the soil. Furthermore, owing to the lower specific gravity of nano-silica compared to the base soil, the MDD of the stabilized soil was reduced during the curing process, resulting in a decrease in the dry weight of the soil. These results align with previous studies demonstrating that nano-silica can improve the MDD of soil significantly (29-31).

4. 2. Effects of Hemp Fiber and Nano-silica on Compaction

Evaluating the soil reinforced with 1% nano-silica and varying percentages of hemp fibers (Figure 4), we found that the MDD of the soil decreased, while the OMC increased with the increase in hemp fiber percentage. These changes were caused by the interaction of water with nano-silica and the water absorption of hemp fibers. In other words, the increase in OMC is due to the presence of silica in nano-silica and the cellulose properties of the hemp fibers.

Figure 3. Results of compaction test for soil with 0% , 0.5%, 1%, and 1.5% nano-silica

Figure 4. Results of compaction test for soil with 1% nano-silica and different percentages of hemp fibers (0.2%, 0.4%, and 0.6%)

Therefore, to achieve the maximum dry density in the soil structure, more moisture is required. As a result of the lower density of nano-silica and hemp fibers compared to the soil, combined with the higher volume, these materials occupy the soil particles. Hence, the addition of hemp fibers reduced the dry density. However, as shown, the effect of nano-silica on the changes in the maximum dry density and moisture was significantly greater than the effect of hemp fibers.

4. 3. Effect of Nano-silica on Compressive Strength

The results of the UCS test for nano-silica stabilized clay at different percentages are presented in Figure 5. It is revealed that increasing the nano-silica content had a notable impact on enhancing the UCS. However, it was observed that for nano-silica amounts exceeding 1%, this effect became negligible, which was confirmed in similar studies (25). The compressive strength was chosen as the criterion for achieving the best mechanical performance, as indicated by the previous research (1, 15). Additionally, Figure 5 reveals that the UCS was almost the same at 1% and 1.5% nano-silica. According to the studies, using higher amounts of nano-silica did not significantly improve the soil properties and was not cost-effective (32). With an increment in the percentage of nano-silica in the soil, the UCS significantly changed. For instance, adding 0.5% nano-silica resulted in a 38% increase in this strength, which further increased to 43% with the addition of 1% nano-silica. However, increasing the nano-silica to 1.5% only contributed to a 5% increase in strength. Thus, it can be concluded that the optimal concentration of nano-silica was 1%. The examination of compressive strengths indicates that the ratio of the maximum UCS to the initial soil for 0.5%, 1%, and 1.5% nano-silica is 1.38, 1.99, and 2.09, respectively. Furthermore, the ratio of the UCS of the residue to the initial soil for these percentages is estimated to be 0.83,

Figure 5. Stress-strain curve of the UCS test for different percentages of nano-silica

0.65, and 0.47, respectively. Similar results suggest that the increase in nano-silica, due to its water absorption, reduces the compressibility of the clay, which is intensified by increasing the percentage of nano-silica. Under such conditions, the use of fibers can prevent cracking in the soil and improve its tensile strength.

This phenomenon is caused by the friction between the fibers and clay particles, which enhances the soil's stability (19). The decrease in residual strength in nano-silica stabilized clay can be attributed to a change in the soil's behavior from ductile to brittle (33). By increasing the percentage of nano-silica, the soil gradually loses its ductility and exhibits a more brittle behavior. This brittleness reduces the ability of the soil to resist post-failure deformations after failure, leading to a decline in residual strength (19). According to Figure 5, adding 1% nano-silica provided the highest compressive strength. Although increasing the nano-silica content further resulted in continued changes in compressive strength, these changes were very limited. For example, increasing the nano-silica content to 1.5% enhanced brittleness and caused the formation of fine cracks in the soil structure, ultimately resulting in only a 5% increase in strength. In the samples containing 1% nano-silica, the greatest improvement in the maximum compressive strength was found compared to the initial soil. However, the residual strength of these samples decreased when compared to the initial soil. This was caused by the reduced voids and enhanced nano-silica-soil interaction. The reason is the production of a sticky gel as a result of the reaction between water and nano-silica. The gel produced strengthens the bonds between particles thus increasing the compressive strength. However, when the nano-silica percentage exceeds 1%, the production of sticky gel surpasses the necessary amount required to bond the soil particles. This not only weakens the strong bonds between the particles but also reduces the strengthening effect. As a result, at percentages higher than 1%, the changes in compressive strength gradually decrease.

These results are in agreement with the findings from similar studies indicating that the production of sticky gel both improves compressive strength and reduces the ductility of the stabilized soil (34, 35). The peak UCS of nano-silica stabilized clay happens at a lower strain compared to the natural clay in all tested samples. However, with increasing nano-silica content, the strain variation decreases, and the specimens exhibit a more brittle behavior. Based on the data shown in Figure 5, the addition of 1% nano-silica reduces the yield strain from 1.8% to 1.28%, equivalent to a 28.8% reduction in this parameter. Moreover, for samples containing 1.5% nano-silica, the yield strain decreases further to 1.2%, representing a 33% reduction compared to natural clay. Numerous studies have demonstrated that exceeding a certain threshold of nanomaterial content diminishes their effectiveness in enhancing the UCS. According to the results of UCS tests depicted in Figure 5, increasing the nano-silica percentage led to an improvement in the peak UCS of the soil, whereas the residual UCS decreased significantly. This is attributed to the structural alterations and interactions between soil particles and nano-silica (9).

As can be observed, the implementation of nano silica typically results in a brittle characteristic in soil samples. The inflexible silica matrix restricts plastic deformation, rendering the soil more fragile. Nano-silica particles can generate rigid zones in the soil, resulting in stress accumulation and restricted energy dissipation. In contrast to clay minerals, which exhibit plastic deformation, a silica-rich matrix typically fractures suddenly when subjected to force (34). As can be seen, the nano-silica also influences the ductility of reinforced soil. Equation 1 shows the ductility index (D), where ϵ_{soil} and $\epsilon_{soil+nanosilica}$ are the failure strain values for untreated and treated soil samples, respectively. A decrease in D correlates with a reduction in ductility. As a result, lower dissipation of energy and higher brittle failure.

$$D = \frac{\epsilon_{soil+nanosilica}}{\epsilon_{soil}} \quad (1)$$

The results indicate that nano silica influences the ductility index of reinforced soil. As can be observed, the failure strain of pure soil is 1.87. However, by adding 0.5%, 1%, and 1.5% of nano silica failure strain reduces to 1.87%, 1.65%, 1.59%, and 1.51%. It means that adding 0.5%, 1%, and 1.5% nano silica decreased the ductility index (D) by about 12%, 15%, and 20%, which means higher brittle behavior and lower ductility. In addition, the residual strength for untreated soil was at the final stage 90.4 kPa, and by adding 0.5, 1, and 1.5% of nano silica, it reduced to 75.6, 59.2, and 42.7 kPa. This shows that lower bearing capacity after failure, which means a stiffer matrix due to the addition of nano silica.

The findings of unconfined compression tests and the variations in E_{50} of clay stabilized with different nano-

silica contents are presented in Figure 6. It is demonstrated that the elastic modulus (E_{50}) of the soil increased with the increment in nano-silica content. The recorded improvement ratios of the elastic modulus for various nano-silica percentages were 1.03 for 0.5%, 1.09 for 1%, and 1.17 for 1.5%. These findings highlight the positive influence of nano-silica on enhancing the stiffness and resistance of the soil against deformation (19). This parameter also called energy absorption capacity, serves as an indicator of the specimens' ductility and the quantity of energy needed for their deformation (1). Known also as the Secant Modulus, it shows the slope of a straight line from the origin to a point equivalent to 1/2 of the maximum stress, indicating the stiffness of the specimens. Due to the distinct softening characteristics of clay, the values of this parameter for natural clay are significantly lower than those for nano-silica-stabilized clay, as illustrated in Figure 6. For natural clay, this parameter is approximately 22,416 kPa, whereas the inclusion of nano-silica increases the values to 33,909 kPa, 45,423 kPa, and 47,003 kPa for samples containing 0.5%, 1%, and 1.5% nano-silica, respectively. These figures reflect the increases of 50%, 102%, and 109% in the E_{50} parameter compared to the natural clay. This enhancement is attributed to the superior energy absorption capability of nano-silica (19). The effects of soil stabilization with nano-silica can be analyzed from two main perspectives. First, when mixed with water, nano-silica forms a viscous gel, which significantly enhances the adhesion between clay particles because of its water absorption and the creation of either a viscous or crystalline structure. As a result, the bonds formed in nano-silica stabilized samples are much stronger than those present in natural clay without nano-silica. These structural changes lead to improved compressive strength and reduced deformability of the soil. The formation of the viscous gel occurs due to the release of silicate bonds existing in nano-silica, which then bind with the hydrogen molecules in water. This process results in the

Figure 6. E_{50} for natural soil and different percentages of nano-silica (0.5%, 1%, and 1.5%)

formation of robust and adhesive structures strengthening the mechanical properties of the soil and preventing excessive deformations (36).

In the second approach, the use of nano-silica enhances surface friction and reduces the spacing between kaolinite particles, resulting in increased contact among the soil particles. This characteristic causes the soil to exhibit denser behavior under stress. Followed by deformation, the frictional forces between the particles increase, thus enhancing the interaction between the nanoparticles and the soil. Ultimately, the friction generated between the particles contributes to the improvement of the strength of the soil matrix. However, the resulting samples typically display a brittle character. Previous studies emphasized that to maintain the flexibility of such samples, the addition of fibers is essential (29, 31).

4. 4. Effect of 1% Nano-silica and Hemp Fiber on Compressive Strength

In Figure 7, the values of UCS for clay stabilized with 1% nano-silica and reinforced with hemp fibers are presented. The results reveal that as the percentage of hemp fibers increases, both the peak and residual UCS values are improved. In previous studies, the identified optimal amount of nano-silica was 1%. With the addition of this amount of nano-silica, the peak UCS increases by 33%, 14%, and 6% compared to the previous sample as the hemp fiber content rises to 0.2%, 0.4%, and 0.6%, respectively. This trend indicates that adding more than 0.4% hemp fibers does not lead to a considerable improvement in strength, with the optimal percentage of hemp fibers as 0.4%. Based on the results, the UCS maximum rate of increment for the mixture containing 0.4% fibers and 1% nano-silica is 2.75 times the corresponding value for natural clay and 1.37 times that of the sample stabilized with 1% nano-silica without fibers. It is revealed that natural fibers when combined with nanomaterials, have a significant effect on the mechanical properties of clay.

Figure 7. Stress-strain curve of the UCS for different fiber percentages (0.4%, 0.6%, and 0.8%) with 1% nano-silica

Furthermore, the fiber-reinforced samples exhibit more ductile behavior. Therefore, the combination of hemp fibers with nano-silica represents a more effective approach for improving the mechanical behavior of clay. This can be related to the interaction between the soil particles and the viscous gel produced by nano-silica, which is further enhanced by the increase in fiber content. In this process, nano-silica forms a sticky gel that covers a substantial portion of the hemp fibers' surface, leading to more effective bonding between the soil particles and fibers. Hence, the roughness of the fiber surfaces increases strengthening the bond between the soil matrix and the reinforcing fibers, ultimately resulting in a substantial improvement in the compressive strength of the soil. Comparing the different fiber percentages, it is revealed that the UCS maximum rate of increment is achieved in samples containing 0.4% fibers. This maximum rate is selected because, as the fiber content increases to higher percentages, the increase in compressive strength is limited to only 6%. As observed in Figure 7, increasing the fiber percentage both improves compressive strength and enhances the ductility and resistance of the soil against stress. The incorporation of an elevated dosage of hemp fiber (more than 0.6%) leads to fiber clumping and inadequate dispersion, as demonstrated by visual examination. Excessive fiber content leads to clustering, aggregation, clogging, and uneven distribution, rather than reinforcing the soil matrix and enhancing homogeneity. At dosage more than 0.6%, fibers tend to aggregate instead of dispersing uniformly, diminishing their efficacy and resulting in reduced fiber-soil adhesion. This results in the formation of frail and susceptible areas instead of augmenting overall resilience. Consequently, this study indicates that the elevated dosage of 0.6% diminished the compressive strength of the soil. Hemp fibers enhance the cohesion and uniformity of the soil and serve a crucial role in reinforcement by creating a three-dimensional network structure formed among the soil particles. These fibers increased structural stability by preventing crack formation and inhibiting excessive soil slippage. This can be explained by the phenomenon of "bridging" which is described in many sources (19). Here, the fibers act as bridges between cracks and soil particles, preventing rupture. Furthermore, the formation of a sticky gel on the surface of the fibers enhanced the interaction between the fibers and the soil. During the curing process of the fiber-reinforced soil stabilized with nano-silica, this gel was attached to the fiber surfaces. Increasing surface roughness and improving the bonding characteristics between the fibers and soil, the interlocking and frictional forces were enhanced. Therefore, the bond between the fibers and the soil was reinforced, significantly enhancing the behavior of the soil under stress. The reaction of water with nano-silica also resulted in the formation of a gel and nanoparticles, which, enhanced

particle contact and improved the internal friction angle within the soil structure by filling the voids. On the other hand, hemp fibers, with their surface roughness and friction, provided a suitable substrate for the attachment of nano-silica, thereby strengthening the interaction between the soil particles and the fibers. However, an excessive increase in the fiber content can negatively affect the interaction between the soil and nano-silica, leading to a reduction in the rate of improvement of compressive strength. Many sources suggest that the use of complementary materials, such as calcium-based additives, can mitigate this limitation and optimize the effects of the combination of fibers and nano-silica (29). The incorporation of nano-silica into clay reduces the strain at yield in the stabilized samples when compared to the natural clay. This is caused by the impact of nano-silica on the soil structure and the formation of stronger bonds between the particles. Moreover, raising the percentage of hemp fibers reduces the brittleness of the stabilized samples and improves their ductile behavior. It was observed that the inclusion of nano-silica induces a sudden yield in the samples. However, increasing the percentage of hemp fibers alters the yielding mechanism and results in a more gradual behavior. This change in the yielding mechanism, along with the increment in fiber content, increases the residual UCS of the samples, demonstrating an improvement in their stability and durability.

In Figure 4, the values of the elastic modulus (E_{50}) of the clay samples stabilized with different percentages of nano-silica, obtained from UCS, are presented. The results show that the optimal elastic modulus, which provides suitable brittleness, is achieved with the addition of 1% nano-silica. Additionally, as shown in Figure 8, the addition of 1% nano-silica significantly increases the elastic modulus of the samples. This increase is 47%, 61%, and 64% for the samples containing 0.2%, 0.4%, and 0.6% hemp fibers, respectively. Notably, the maximum increase in elastic modulus was recorded for the sample containing 0.2% fibers and 1% nano-silica. This behavior can be associated with the positive effect of hemp fibers in reducing the brittleness of the samples. Hemp fibers, by improving the ductile behavior of the soil and reducing brittleness, have been able to create better interaction among the components of the sample and enhance its mechanical properties. These results emphasize the importance of simultaneously using nano-silica and fibers in optimizing the mechanical features of the soil. Ductility is an essential characteristic of geotechnical structures, allowing materials to undergo substantial deformation before failing, thereby increasing their strength and reliability. In structures like retaining walls, embankments, and foundations, ductility helps redistribute stresses, preventing abrupt and disastrous failures. This feature is particularly crucial in regions

Figure 8. E_{50} for 1% nano-silica and different fiber percentages (0.2%, 0.4%, and 0.6%)

prone to earthquakes, as ductile behavior absorbs seismic energy and minimizes structural damage (1). Furthermore, ductile materials and designs enhance resistance to cyclic loading, including freeze-thaw cycles and traffic-induced vibrations, lowering the likelihood of cracking and long-term degradation (5). By facilitating controlled deformation instead of brittle failure, ductility improves the performance, flexibility, and overall stability of geotechnical systems, ensuring their dependability under diverse environmental and loading conditions.

4. 5. Effect of Freeze-thaw Cycles To investigate the behavior of clay under F-T cycles, three types of samples were tested including natural clay, clay stabilized with the optimal percentage of nano-silica, and clay stabilized with 1% nano-silica and reinforced with 0.4% hemp fibers. Understanding the temperature range and duration of freeze-thaw cycles is essential for soil stabilization efforts in practical engineering applications. The F-T cycle can impact the stability and durability of constructions, such as roads, buildings, and bridges, as well as soil structure. The structural, physical, and mechanical properties of the soil are profoundly affected by freeze-thaw cycles. In certain locations, temperatures can plummet to -15 to -20 degrees Celsius in winter, while summer temperatures often range from 22 to 30 degrees Celsius. Thus, temperatures ranging from -18 to 25 degrees Celsius were considered indicative of realistic engineering situations. Additionally, to account for the worst-case situation, the freezing cycle for each sample is assumed to endure for 24 hours, according to prior studies. The identical time and period was also taken into account for the thawing cycle. This time is necessary for the creation and dissolution of ice crystals at the temperatures, as stated in literature (38-46).

Figure 9 illustrates the variations in compressive strength of the soil under F-T cycles (1, 3, 5, 7, and 10)

for the optimal additive percentages (0.4% hemp fibers and 1% nano-silica). As seen, the final strength of natural soil significantly decreased with an increment in the number of cycles. After 10 cycles, the strength of the untreated soil decreased by approximately 55%.

In contrast, the samples stabilized with nano-silica and hemp fibers showed much less strength reduction. For the samples containing 1% nano-silica and 0.4% hemp fibers, the strength reduction in the tenth cycle was only about 11%. These results suggest that the incorporation of nano-silica and fibers not only improves the strength of the soil but also significantly enhances its stability under F-T cycles. An analysis of the changes in UCS of the soil under F-T cycles revealed that the greatest strength reduction in the natural soil samples occurred between the 5th and 7th cycles. At this stage, the soil strength decreased from 175 kPa (after 5 cycles) to 133 kPa (after 7 cycles). With the continuation of the cycles and reaching the tenth cycle, the rate of strength reduction slowed down, and the strength of the natural soil eventually stabilized at 122 kPa. This trend reflects a gradual reduction in the impact of F-T cycles in the later stages. For the samples stabilized with 1% nano-silica and 0.4% hemp fibers, a different behavior was observed. In these samples, as the number of cycles increased from 1 to 7, the rate of compressive strength reduction increased. However, in the tenth cycle, this rate stabilized. The greatest strength reduction in these samples occurred between cycles 5 and 7, with the strength decreasing from 691 kPa (in cycle 5) to 663 kPa (in cycle 7). These results suggest that stabilizing the soil with nano-silica and hemp fibers effectively mitigates the detrimental effects of F-T cycles and prevents a significant drop in strength. Additionally, soil stabilization helps control the rate of strength reduction in the final cycles, indicating greater stability of these samples under repeated freezing conditions. The findings

Figure 9. Maximum stress (UCS) of soil under F-T cycles (with cycles 0, 1, 3, 5, 7, and 10) for soil and soil with 1% nano-silica and 0.4% hemp fibers

of this study are consistent with those reported in previous research, particularly regarding the formation and degradation of ice lenses in clayey soils (6). As observed, the UCS of both untreated samples and those stabilized and reinforced with additives decreased with the increasing number of F-T cycles. However, the strength reduction in untreated samples was significantly greater. Adding nano-silica and hemp fibers to natural soil improved the initial strength of the samples. This enhancement, especially before the F-T cycles, can be ascribed to the water absorption and the formation of a sticky silicate gel by the nano-silica. However, the negative impact of moisture on hemp fibers led to a gradual reduction in strength as the number of cycles increased. Nevertheless, the intensity of strength reduction in the reinforced samples was much lower than in the untreated samples. Clay shows a significant reduction in strength because of its inherent weakness in load-bearing capacity and high susceptibility to F-T cycles. Therefore, stabilizing and reinforcing it with nano-silica and hemp fibers was introduced as an effective solution for improving the strength of the soil and its resistance to freezing conditions (19). Ultimately, the reinforced samples exhibited much better performance under F-T cycles. As shown in Figure 9, after 10 cycles, the positive changes in strength in the reinforced samples decreased, although they still performed better than the unreinforced soil. These results highlight the importance of using a combination of stabilizing and reinforcing materials to improve the mechanical properties of the soil.

To compare the effect of F-T cycles on UCS, the resistance reduction coefficient (UCS reduction ratio) parameter is defined as Equation 2:

$$Re = \frac{\sigma_{F-T} - \sigma_{Untreated}}{\sigma_{Untreated}} \quad (2)$$

where Re is the resistance reduction coefficient, $\sigma_{Untreated}$ is the maximum UCS stress for natural soil, and σ_{F-T} is the maximum unconfined stress after each F-T cycle.

The UCS reduction ratio was calculated and presented in Figure 10. As seen, the UCS reduction ratio in untreated soil was higher significantly than in stabilized soil, nearly five times greater. It is proved that the use of the sticky gel produced by nano-silica and the presence of reinforcing elements such as hemp fibers effectively increased the resistance of the soil and prevented its degradation. To mitigate the adverse effects of moisture on the fibers and further enhance the soil's properties, chemical treatment of the hemp fibers could be considered prior to their incorporation into the soil (9). Chemical treatment reduces the water absorption of the fibers and increases the bonding between the fibers and the soil. This process both enhances and strengthens the surface and physical properties of the fibers, resulting in improved mechanical performance of the stabilized soil.

Figure 10. Reduction coefficient (Re) of soil resistance under F-T cycles (with cycles 0, 1, 3, 5, 7, and 10) for soil and soil with 1% nano-silica and 0.4% hemp fibers

To contextualize the findings of this study, a comparison was made with conventional stabilization methods, considering both mechanical performance and environmental impact. The optimal condition identified in this study led to a 10-fold increase in UCS. In comparison, a previous study showed that incorporating 3% cement in kaolinite soil achieved a 15-fold increase in UCS (47). However, the heavy reliance on cement results in substantial CO₂ emissions, making it a less sustainable option despite its strength benefits. Similarly, another study utilizing 3% lime in clayey soil showed only a 1.6-fold increase in UCS, underscoring the relatively lower efficiency of lime stabilization under similar conditions (48). Additionally, research on clay composites with over 6% cement demonstrated a 9-fold UCS improvement but came with significant environmental concerns due to the high carbon footprint of cement (49). Comparing these findings with existing literature, the use of nano-silica and hemp fibers presents a promising alternative, significantly enhancing the strength of the clay matrix while offering a more sustainable solution. These findings highlight the high potential of combining nano-silica and chemically treated fibers to enhance the resistance and stability of clayey soils under adverse environmental conditions.

It is worth highlighting that past studies indicate that most of the physical and mechanical changes in soils, such as loss of strength, rise in permeability, or volumetric changes, occur within the first few cycles (31, 45). After approximately 10 cycles, the rate of change generally declines, rendering subsequent cycles less significant. In addition, any engineering and geotechnical standards, such as ASTM, AASHTO, and other national guidelines, recommend 10 freeze-thaw cycles as a benchmark for soil stabilization and construction material testing (1, 6). The recommendation gives a standard base for comparing findings across studies and

initiatives. It is noteworthy that as the number of F-T cycles increased to 10, the rate of change in UCS diminished, ultimately attaining a nearly constant rate and equilibrium.

4. 6. XRD Test

Figure 11 illustrates the X-ray diffraction (XRD) patterns of natural clay and samples stabilized with 1% nano-silica. To investigate the presence or absence of chemical reactions between nano-silica and soil, the stabilized samples were subjected to XRD testing following 28 days of curing. The results indicated that the XRD patterns of the natural clay sample contained silica, calcite oxide, alumina, and other essential soil minerals. In the nano-silica-stabilized samples, no notable changes in the mineral composition were detected. Moreover, no new peaks appeared in the XRD patterns. These results suggest that the combination of nano-silica with water did not induce a substantial chemical reaction with the soil particles.

The XRD patterns reveal that the primary mineral components of kaolinite clay consist of silica (S), aluminum (A), calcium oxide (Ca), and iron (I) minerals. As can be seen kaolinite main peak intensities are between 12.4°, 21.5°, 27.3°, 47.2° and 67.5°. XRD analysis and microscopic examination revealed that the clay particles are mostly plate-shaped, with their edges primarily exhibiting prismatic shapes. The principal and

Figure 11. XRD test results for natural soil and soil with 1% nano-silica

most significant peaks identified indicate that the majority of clay particles are arranged in layers, aligning with the conclusions of (35).

The minerals that constitute kaolinite mostly consist of silica and aluminum phases. These minerals induce a peak in the XRD curve as a result of electron interaction with silica and aluminum minerals. Conversely, the integration of nano silica into kaolinite soil samples does not produce a significant change in the major peak angles. The principal peaks in the XRD curve remain the same with the addition of nano silica to the designated soils. This outcome is elucidated by the filling effect of the nano silica due to hydrogen bonding and Van der Waals. In kaolinite soil, a slight alteration between peaks occurs due to hydrogen bonding. Additionally, the nano silica utilized in this study served as a standard filler between the silica and aluminum layers, affecting the interaction of the silica layers (29). Moreover, soil stabilization utilizing nano silica enhances the intensity of some principal peaks. In other words, nano silica exhibit adhesive properties owing to their natural origin and inert qualities when combined with water or hydrogen and oxygen molecules (H₂O). This contrasts with traditional stabilizers that enhance hydration and pozzolanic interactions among soil particles and chemical additions. Consequently, the incorporation of nano silica into kaolinite soils produces intermolecular forces, including hydrogen bonding, ionic interactions, electrostatic interactions, and van der Waals forces, which essentially improves mechanical properties. In summary, inert nano silica particles do not experience phase transitions; they merely amplify the strength of the peaks (11). It can be concluded that the main components of nano-silica and natural clay, namely silica and alumina, do not exhibit any noticeable chemical reactions under experimental conditions. Therefore, the effects of nano-silica are more attributed to its physical and mechanical properties, such as filling voids, increasing soil compaction, and improving the bonding between particles. Similar results were seen in study of (37).

4. 7. SEM and EDS Analysis

Scanning electron microscopy (SEM) image analysis was performed to investigate the effects of nano-silica and hemp fibers on the structure of clay soil (Figure 12). These images show significant structural changes in the soil after the application of these stabilizing and reinforcing materials. As can be seen in Figure 12-a, the pure kaolinite sample consisted of numerous fragile sheets exhibiting considerable water absorption capacity due to their multilayered structure, as depicted in Figure 12-a. In other words, the soil sample contains numerous flaky kaolinite particles with significant interstitial voids. The increasing amount of these openings ultimately results in a decrease in the sample's strength, as found by UCS. As can be seen in the SEM analysis, the addition of nano

silica can change the soil matrix significantly (Figure 12-b). Owing to their exceptionally small size and texture, nano silica can serve as filler materials, effectively diminishing inner-particle voids and spaces, hence enhancing mechanical strength. Incorporation of nanosilica densifies the microstructure of kaolinite soil by occupying pores and microcracks, consequently improving the overall behavior of the soil matrix through the formation of nanocrystals. A significantly decreased spacing ratio among soil particles in nano-stabilised soils leads to a more rigid skeletal matrix. Secondly, these nano silica function as particles that efficiently fill the micro-pores between the kaolinite particles, a phenomenon known as the "packing effect" or "filling effect" (50-53). Semi pozzolanic reactions between clay particles and nano-silica led to the formation of a viscous gel that gradually filled the gaps between soil particles, creating strong bonds and increasing their adhesion over time. This process, as shown in Figure 12-a, not only significantly reduced the number of pores and cracks in the soil structure compared to untreated soil, but also led to the formation of a more compact and stable system. Furthermore, nano-silica played a key role in filling the voids and reducing the gaps between soil particles (39). The adhesive property of nano-silica gel is much stronger than the adhesion created by water between soil particles. Figure 12-c represents samples of natural clay and hemp fibers containing numerous flaky particles. These particles are dispersed and arranged with large gaps between them. The presence of these pores and gaps leads to a decrease in the mechanical strength of the soil, a phenomenon that has also been revealed in previous studies (38). By adhering to the surface of hemp fibers, nano-silica increases the contact and bonding between soil particles and prevents the formation of microcracks in soil samples. This property is especially noticeable when nano-silica is present in the form of an adhesive gel or a dry state on the surface of hemp fibers (Figure 12-c). This process leads to the formation of a cohesive and interconnected soil representing improved mechanical performance (40). Mechanical adhesion is also created due to the application of compressive stress to the soil and the plastic deformation of the fibers, which causes the fibers to act as anchors in the soil. Besides, the attachment of soil particles and nano-silica to the fiber surface forms an effective mechanical bond increasing the strength and stability of the soil (39). The formation of flocculated particles as a result of short-term cation exchange processes is also clearly visible in SEM images (Figure 12-d).

Therefore, the bonding of soil particles is enhanced while increasing the strength of the sample (28). As shown in Figure 12-d, the integration of nano-silica and hemp fibers increases the mechanical strength and durability of the samples by distributing stress over a wider area and preventing crack propagation. This

process is quite similar to the function of plant roots in nature, which plays a significant role in soil stabilization and crack reduction. Overall, the combination of nano-silica and hemp fibers not only strengthens the internal bonds of the soil but also significantly increases the resistance of the soil to loading and environmental stresses by creating mechanisms similar to those found in nature.

(a)

(b)

(c)

(d)

Figure 12. SEM images a) kaolinite soil, b) soil and nano, c) soil and fiber d) soil, fiber and nano

EDS analysis was utilized to demonstrate the spectrum of elements present in nano silica soils (Figure 13a, b). The incorporation of nano silica into soil results in EDS spectra that typically exhibit elevated peaks of silica (Si) and aluminum (Al), signifying the presence of nano silica on soil particles. This viscous gel covering, more evident at elevated concentrations (1%), indicates a uniform distribution of nano silica throughout the soil matrix (11). The coating properties of viscous gel from nano silica enhance particle cohesion and bonding, hence offering resistance to shear forces and augmenting compressive strength. The increased elemental density enhances mechanical performance by restricting particle movement. The EDS analysis of unstabilized samples indicates that silica (Si) and aluminum (Al) are the primary components of the soil. An EDS examination of nanosilica soil reveals more Si elements (54). Moreover, elevated concentrations of Si and Al in kaolinite soil enhance the interaction between soil particles and nano silica, attributable to the presence of Al^{3+} in octahedral sites and Si^{4+} in tetrahedral sites in nano silica (54). The phenomenon is ion bridging, wherein silica ions interact with the viscous gel of nanoparticles, hence enhancing the strength and stability of the soil matrix. It is noteworthy that the comparison of the EDS patterns of kaolinite subsequent to the addition of 1% nano silica reveals no new chemical compounds.

5. LIFE CYCLE ASSESSMENT (LCA)

LCA is a common methodology for evaluating sustainability potential, cost-effectiveness, and material efficacy. This assessment highlights the ecological benefits and possible financial savings of nano silica and hemp fiber relative to traditional stabilizers, including cement, lime, gypsum, bitumen, and synthetic fiber like

Figure 13. EDS graph a) soil B) soil + nano silica

polyurethane and polypropylene. In extensive applications at specified locations, the expenses associated with traditional stabilizers may be up to thrice greater than those of nano silica. Moreover, the requirement for higher dosages (generally more than 5%) of traditional stabilizers can substantially elevate their associated expenses. The cost of nano silica has significantly diminished during the last five years, mainly attributable to its expansion in industrial applications. The cost of 1 ton of nano silica has diminished from around \$520 USD 150 USD during the past decade, reflecting a decrease of nearly 370 USD. Conversely, silica, the second most prevalent element on the Earth's surface, can be simply transformed into NS, which is both economically feasible and easily obtainable. Moreover, hemp fiber, a natural fiber utilized as a soil-reinforcing agent, is obtained from extensively cultivated plants and necessitates minimal industrial processing. Table 7 outlines the material costs related to the suggested use of nano silica and hemp fiber as biocompatible materials for soil stabilization. The prices enumerated in this table exclude transportation and on-site labor expenses, which may vary based on the project's location and scale (49). Local merchants of these eco-friendly goods have supplied the standard pricing illustrated in Table 7, as these costs may fluctuate based on regulatory regulations

TABLE 7. Cost estimations for nano silica, hemp fiber, and other traditional additives in soil improvement

Additives	Price of 1 ton (USD)	CO ₂ per ton (ton)
Nano silica	150-200	0.01-0.02
Hemp fiber	7-10	0.002-0.006
Cement	90-260	0.9 to 1.1
Lime	85-140	0.88-1.4
Bitumen	190-330	1-1.3
Synthetic fibers	160-220	0.3-0.5

in different countries. Conventional binders, like cement and lime, are acknowledged for their significant strength contributions; however, their long-term sustainability is increasingly scrutinized because to high energy consumption, potential leaching effects, and CO₂ emissions. Conversely, the innovative bio-compatible materials utilized in this work, including nano silica and hemp fiber, provide a more sustainable alternative while achieving significant mechanical enhancements. This study highlights that these materials deliver an effective soil stabilization solution with minimal environmental concerns, rendering them especially appropriate for sustainable infrastructure development in extreme climates and cold regions where freeze-thaw durability is a big concern.

6. CONCLUSION

The use of environmentally friendly materials has always been a major concern in civil engineering. In this study, for the first time, the effect of combining hemp fibers as a reinforcement and nano-silica as a soil stabilizer was investigated to increase the durability and strength of clay soil. Then, the effect of different ratios of these materials on the durability and strength of soil samples against successive F-T cycles was assessed.

For this purpose, UCS experiments were conducted to determine the effectiveness of combining hemp fibers and nano-silica on soil samples at the macro and micro scales. At the macro scale, the durability and strength of the samples were investigated under the influence of additives. At the micro scale, SEM imaging and X-ray diffraction (XRD) were used to investigate the structural and chemical properties of the samples. The results of these analyses shed light on the reinforcing effects and mechanisms of these materials on clay soil. The key findings of this study showed that combining hemp fibers and nano-silica has positive effects on the durability and mechanical and structural properties of clay soil. These findings are summarized as follows:

The maximum improvement in compressive strength was found with an optimum content of 1% nano-silica. In

the case of stabilization with 1% nano-silica, the addition of 0.4% hemp fibers was the most effective ratio for improving soil strength. The combination of nano-silica and hemp fibers increased the cohesion and friction between particles in the soil.

The addition of hemp fibers improved soil ductility. In contrast, nano-silica reduced soil ductility by creating stiffer structures. The simultaneous use of both materials increased the friction and interlocking between soil particles and significantly improved the compressive strength of the reinforced soil. The hemp fibers helped to bind the soil particles together and close the gaps in the fracture zones. The nano-silica created a cohesive gel between the soil particles, which created a stronger bond between the soil particles and prevented cracking. These factors increased the compressive strength and the ability of the soil to withstand deformation without failure.

The soil reinforced with fibers and nano-silica showed greater durability against F-T cycles. These materials helped prevent cracking and reduce soil degradation due to freezing and thawing. Hemp fibers increased the soil pressure before failure and changed the soil behavior from brittle to ductile.

The stabilizers used were environmentally friendly materials, which can be a good alternative to traditional stabilizers. The combination of hemp fibers and nano-silica as stabilizers for clay soils increased mechanical strength and durability and offered a good option for civil engineering applications because of its environmental and economic benefits. The research also highlighted the key role of microstructures (viscous gel and particle locking) in improving soil properties.

According to findings, the incorporation of road nano silica and hemp fiber can be used in various geo-structures. Nano-silica enhances soil bonding and compressive strength in subgrades and pavement layers. In addition, hemp fibers improve flexibility and prevent cracking due to shrinkage and F-T cycles and lead to increased bearing capacity, reducing deformation under traffic loads. In addition, hemp fibers can be used as natural reinforcement in embankments and slope stabilization which can improve tensile strength, reducing erosion and soil slippage. Application of nano-silica reduces and prevents surface erosion, improves long-term stability permeability and enhances cohesion. In addition, according to the improvement ratio of compressive strength, nano silica and hemp fiber can be utilized in enhancing expansive lay stabilization Nano-silica reacts with clay minerals, forming viscous gels that reduce swelling. Hemp fibers prevent shrinkage cracking, improving load distribution on weak soils.

7. FUTURE TREND

Like other materials, large-scale applications of nano silica and hemp fiber face certain limitations, and the

challenges of mass production have been recognized. The study highlights ongoing gaps in understanding its efficiency, interactions, and failure mechanisms in geo-environments. Therefore, extensive testing and computational modeling are necessary to better analyze the compressive and shear behavior of bio-stabilized, fiber-reinforced soil. Additionally, optimizing fiber ratios, diameters, and configurations is crucial for broader applications. A thorough large-scale study of ageing effects on hemp fiber-reinforced soil strength is needed, as research in this area remains limited. More research is also required on fiber manipulation and the impact of temperature on randomly distributed fibers. A key drawback of hemp fiber reinforcement is its gradual degradation, which weakens interlocking forces and reduces adhesion with the soil matrix. Water absorption alters fiber microstructure, causing cell wall swelling and deterioration, ultimately compromising strength and durability. Enhancing fiber durability in soil remains a critical research area. This study primarily assessed the composite behavior of nano silica and hemp fiber, but large-scale evaluations are necessary to determine its long-term performance and durability under wetting-drying cycles and high-temperature conditions. In addition, conducting cyclic loading and shear strength tests to evaluate additional geotechnical performance aspects needs further investigation.

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Persian Abstract**چکیده**

چرخه‌های یخ و ذوب (F-T) می‌توانند به طور قابل توجهی بر خواص ژئوتکنیکی خاک تأثیر بگذارند. بنابراین، در مناطقی با پتانسیل یخ زدگی و ذوب بالا، در نظر گرفتن اثرات این چرخه‌ها در زمان تحلیل دوام و تغییر شکل شیب‌ها و گودبرداری‌ها ضروری است. یکی از روش‌های موثر برای بهبود خواص مکانیکی خاک‌های رسی تحت چرخه یخ زدگی و ذوب، تثبیت خاک با نانوذرات و الیاف طبیعی است. در این مطالعه، تأثیر چرخه‌های یخ زدگی و ذوب بر پارامترهای مقاومتی خاک‌های رسی تقویت‌شده با نانو سیلیس و الیاف کنف مورد بررسی قرار گرفت. آزمایش‌هایی برای تعیین اثر نانو سیلیس (SiO_2) و الیاف کنف بر مقاومت فشاری نامحدود (UCS) تحت چرخه‌های یخ زدگی و ذوب انجام شد. نمونه‌های خاک با ۰.۵٪، ۱٪ و ۱.۵٪ نانو سیلیس تثبیت شدند. سپس نمونه‌ها با درصد الیاف به خاک ۰.۲٪، ۰.۴٪ و ۰.۶٪ و درصد بهینه نانو سیلیس ۱ درصد تهیه شد. سپس، نمونه‌ها تحت ۱، ۳، ۵، ۷ و ۱۰ چرخه یخ زدگی و ذوب برای آزمایش دوام قرار گرفتند. در نهایت، آزمایش‌های UCS برای تعیین استحکام هر دو نمونه تقویت‌شده و خاک طبیعی انجام شد. بر اساس نتایج آزمایشات UCS، میزان بهینه نانو سیلیس ۱ درصد بود که مقاومت خاک را ۹۲ درصد افزایش داد. با توجه به آزمایشات UCS، زمانی که ۱٪ نانو سیلیس در خاک استفاده شد، حداکثر مقاومت فشاری به دست آمد که معیار عملکرد مکانیکی بهینه است. نتایج آزمایش‌های UCS بر روی نمونه‌های آزمایش دوام، با افزایش تعداد چرخه‌ها برای نمونه‌های تقویت‌نشده، کاهش ۲۷ تا ۵۰ درصدی در UCS را نشان داد. با این حال، ترکیب ۱٪ نانو سیلیس و ۰.۴٪ الیاف کنف منجر به کاهش ۱۳٪ در UCS خاک پس از ۱۰ چرخه انجماد و ذوب شد، در حالی که مقاومت UCS برای خاک تثبیت‌نشده تا ۵۰٪ کاهش یافت. مناطق به هم پیوسته و افزایش اصطکاک بین ذرات با استفاده از الیاف کنف بین دانه‌های خاک و نانو سیلیس بهبود یافت. در نتیجه، این پدیده‌ها به طور موثری از ترک بیش از حد در طول استفاده از چرخه‌های F-T جلوگیری می‌کنند و در نتیجه عملکرد مکانیکی و دوام نمونه‌ها را افزایش می‌دهند.